

RELATIONS OF GREAT BRITAIN WITH BUKHARA IN THE XIX CENTURY

Tojiyev Bobur

Doctoral Student Of Uzbekistan State University Of World Languages, Uzbekistan

Abstract: This article analyzes the relations between Bukhara and Afghanistan in the international relations between the Russian Empire, Great Britain and the Ottoman Turkish Empire in the 1970s. Also, trade and economic relations between the Emirate of Bukhara and Afghanistan in the last quarter of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century are considered and researched.

Keywords: Afghanistan, Sherah Khan, Bukhara, Ottoman Turkish Empire, the Russo-Turkish war, Bendar-Abbas-Mashhad road, Central Asia, ambassadors, Ost-Indian company.

As a result of the transformation of the Bukhara Emirate into a dependent state of the Russian Empire, the Emirate was deprived of the right to conduct an active foreign policy. This situation damaged the reputation of the Bukhara Emirate as one of the political leaders in the Eastern Muslim world. Since the 70s of the 19th century, the place and role of Bukhara in the region and international relations has also decreased. In the 70s of the 19th century, there were conflicts between the states of Bukhara and Afghanistan, which gained regional and international importance. The conflict between the Uzbek principalities on the left bank of the Amudarya has a territorial character, and during the colonial process these conflicts grew to the level of international relations. It was important for the Russian Empire to keep the Emirate of Bukhara under control and to improve relations with the country of Afghanistan in order to prevent the British from invading Central Asia. During this period, the ruler of Afghanistan, Sherah Khan, and the governor-general of Turkestan, K.P. von Kaufman had a warm relationship. Correspondence and exchange of letters between the two continued from March 28, 1870 until Sherah Khan's death in 1879[1]. This made it possible to keep Afghanistan neutral in the Russian-Turkish war of 1877-1878. In Afghanistan, the Anglo-Turkish alliance tried to replace Sherah Khan with a person inclined to the new British policy, and to create an alliance against the Russians in Bukhara. For example, in 1875, the emir of Bukhara, Muzaffar Khan, requested the governor-general of Turkestan to release Abdurrahman Khan, the nephew of Sherah Khan, who was living as a fugitive in Samarkand. It was natural that such a request of the Bukhara emir aroused suspicion in the Russian political authorities. On the other hand, the emir of Bukhara demanded the return of the Maimana principality, which was captured in 1874, although he was forbidden to act in foreign political matters without Russia's permission. The emir of Bukhara called Maimana his vassal and demanded the return of this

territory from Afghanistan in 1875 and tried to make the Russian Empire war with Afghanistan. This situation made it more difficult for the British-Turkish alliance to fight against Russia by uniting Afghanistan and Bukhara[2]. The authorities of the Russian Empire felt it important to keep England neutral in the impending war with Turkey, and close relations between the Governor-General of Turkestan and Afghanistan were a guarantee of this. The reason why Sherah Khan did not join the alliance against Russia was the occupation of Kelat and Quetta regions of Afghanistan by the British. The sensitive point in the British policy is India, Bukhara's dependence on Russia, Afghanistan's inclination towards the Russians allowed Russia to quickly approach the border of India, and the British were worried about the possible attacks of the Russians[3]. After 1876, many Turkish emissaries began to enter Bukhara through Kabul. It is noted in the historical literature that it was especially intensified on the eve of the Russo-

Turkish war. In April 1877, the ambassadors of the Turkish sultan came to Kabul and offered to fight against the Russians in alliance with Afghanistan and get help from the British. However, at this time, political and diplomatic relations between Sheralikhon and Kaufman were well established, and Sheralikhon K.P. was aware of the proposals and intentions of the Turks[4]. warned von Kaufman. The ambassador of the Ottoman Turkish Empire, who arrived in Kabul and was greeted with great ceremony, Ahmad Khulusi Effendi, told Sherali Khan that the Ottoman Turks had started a war against the Russians, that all Muslims should participate in it, and that the emir of Afghanistan should join the struggle together with the state of Bukhara[5]. Famous scientist N.A. Khalfin Ahmad Khulusi Effendi noted that he brought a letter from the Ottoman Turkish sultan to the ruler of Afghanistan. In the letter, the Ottoman Turkish sultan offered Sherali Khan to fight against the Russians in alliance with the British, and cooperate in freeing Bukhara and Khiva from the Russians. A. D. Vasilev also gave information about Ahmad Khulusi Effendi's activities in Kabul, and the need to unite all Muslims during the Russo-Turkish war of 1877-1878, to use the war to liberate Bukhara and Khiva from Russia, with the support of the Turkmen and Bukharans for the Afghans in this regard. cites related information which suggests that there was an attempt to unite Bukhara and the rival Afghans into an alliance. In Bukhara, Ottoman Turkish propagandists were also engaged in creating anti-Russian sentiment by spreading various rumors. In one of the reports distributed in 1877, it was reported that the British had armed 100,000 Afghan troops against the Russians, and that 35,000 British troops were stationed in Peshawar, and that if the emir of Bukhara violated the treaty with Turkey, these troops would occupy Bukhara and incorporate it into the Afghan state[6]. In 1877, the ambassadors of the Turkish Sultan came to Kabul and Bukhara several times and called on the countries of Bukhara and Afghanistan to cooperate with the British and improve relations[7]. This is the basis for concluding that during the Russian-Turkish war, preparations were made to open another front against the Russian Empire through the Bukhara-Afghan alliance in Central Asia. According to D.N. Logofet, who is in favor of annexing the Bukhara Emirate to the Russian Empire, Bukhara's dependence on Russia, Afghanistan's pro-Russian policy during the Russo-Turkish War, and during the Anglo-Afghan War that started later, Northern Afghanistan (South Turkestan), that is, to the former Bukhara Emirate He emphasized that it was possible to annex the territories of the Uzbek principalities to the protectorate of the Russian Empire[8]. In conclusion, it can be said that on the eve of the Russo-Turkish war of 1877-1878, the British-Turkish alliance of Bukhara and Afghanistan tried to open a new war front in Central Asia by forming a mutual alliance against the Russian Empire. The Emirate of Bukhara had diplomatic and trade-economic relations with countries such as Russia, Iran, Afghanistan, and India in the last quarter of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th.

REFERENCES:

1. Бухара и Афганистан в начале 80-х годов XIX в. (журналы командировки Г.А. Арендаренко). –М.: Главная редакция восточной литературы издательство Наука, 1974. –140 с.
2. Наши дела в Бухаре от вступления в управление краем генерал Кауфмана. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 6. –С. 137. –С. 133-139.
3. Индийский вопрос в Англии. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 8. –С. 293-295.
4. Известия из Туркестанского генерал-губернаторства. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 8. –С. 129-131.
5. Сакт-Петербург. // Туркестанский сборник. Том 41. –С. 201-205.
6. Южаков Ю. Абдурахманхан Афганский. // Туркестанский сборник. Том. 373. – С. 159-174.
7. Терентьев М. Частная корреспонденция “Рускаго инвалида”. // Туркестанский сборник. Том. 7. –С. 89а-89д.
8. Д.Н. Логофет. На границах Средней Азии. Путевые очерки в 3-х книгах. –СПб., 1909; Он же. Страна бесправия. Бухарское ханство и его современное состояние. –СПб., 1909.
9. М.Вирский. Пути сообщения // Справочная книжка Самаркандской области на 1894 г.. Вып. II. –Самарканд, 1894. –С. 180
10. Венюков М.И. Опыт военного обозрения русских границ в Азии. Вып. I.–СПб., 1873. –347-357.
11. А.П.Субботин. Россия и Англия на среднеазиатских рынках. (историко-экономический этюд А.П.Субботина), –СПб., 1885. . 1-3.
12. М.И.Венюков. Опыт военного обозрения русских границ в Азии. Вып. I. – Самарканд, 1873. –С.С. 347-351.

